

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 18, No. 2

Dear Readers,

It is a great honor to take over as Managing Editor of J.UCS from Herman Maurer with the first regular issue of volume 18.

First of all, I would like to take this opportunity to thank Hermann on behalf of all editors-in-chief, members of the J.UCS editorial board, authors and readers for his visionary initiative launching this journal covering all aspects of computer science almost 20 years ago. An initiative which proved not only to be successful, but also sustainable for nearly two decades – a true achievement in the fast-changing world of electronic publishing. As early as 1994, J.UCS had started with its very first volume as a combined online and print journal with the aim not only to increase accessibility of articles and making use of new innovative features, but also of guaranteeing stability and citability of all published papers. Over the years, another important advantage proved to be J.UCS publication policy: open to all topics, open access with no submission or subscription fees. Here I'd like to specifically thank the members of the J.UCS consortium of research organizations for supporting the journal and particularly the Graz University of Technology for its long-standing financial support.

I will continue to follow these strategies and policies to sustain J.UCS as a scientific journal and platform for high-quality and free-accessible papers covering a broad variety of subjects in computer science.

I look forward to collaborating with all editors-in-chief and the members of our editorial board, the editorial team and the technical support to continue the success of J.UCS. Please do continue your support of the journal, sign up for reviews, encourage your colleagues and students to submit high-quality articles and draw attention to the journal whenever possible. I would be also very grateful for any suggestions and feedback on how we could even further improve and develop J.UCS in the next years.

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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